

NASIGuide: MARC CODING FOR SERIALS

by Elizabeth McDonald and Beverly Geckle

September 2008

Introduction

General Comments

Aimed at helping in the creation and interpretation of MARC bibliographic records for serials, this guide focuses on how serial MARC records differ from records for other formats. While continuing resources include both serials and integrating resources such as looseleafs or websites, this guide discusses serials only. Cataloging Serials involves an understanding of both the MARC codes and cataloging rules and practices. Although cataloging rules and practices are referred to, the main focus of this guide is on MARC coding, and not all subfields are always covered.

Serials cataloging rules and practices have changed over the years, so records created based on older rules and practices still exist. The most recent major revision to AACR2 Chapter 12 occurred in 2002. Some older practices are still considered valid while others are not, therefore it is important to be familiar with both current and previous rules and practices. When copy cataloging consider whether the record needs upgrading. New records should be cataloged according to current rules, standards, and practices.

This guide relied heavily on other sources, especially [Marc 21 Format for Bibliographic Data](#), [OCLC's Bibliographic Formats and Standards](#), and [CONSER documentation](#). Other sources either consulted in developing this guide or suggested as resources for further information are listed at the end of this document, see: [RESOURCES](#).

CONSER

CONSER practices are useful guidelines followed by both CONSER and non-CONSER libraries, so they are included here. CONSER has adopted a new standard for creating records. This "Standard Record" describes the minimal requirements for a new serial record. It is important to be familiar with this, since many new records found in OCLC may follow this standard. See: [CONSER Standard Record Documentation](#), the [CONSER Standard Record Cheat Sheet](#) or the [CONSER Standard Record for Serials \(powerpoint\)](#).

Title Changes

Another significant change since 2002 has been new rules regarding title changes and when to create new records. Although these new rules are not discussed in depth it is recommended that one become familiar with them. While new records should be created according to the new rules, older records created under older rules that were valid when they were created can still be used. The following sources are helpful to understanding the current title change rules:

- [Transforming AACR2: Using the revised rules in Chapters 9 and 12](#)
- Chapter 16.2 of the [CONSER Cataloging Manual](#)
- Chapter 21.2C of [AACR2](#)
- The [SCCTP \(Serial Cataloging Cooperative Training Program\)](#) offers useful workshops. The trainee manuals are valuable resources. Descriptions can be found on the Cataloging Distribution Service's [Training Tools](#) website.

Electronic Journals

The MARC fields important to electronic journals are included, but since this guide is focused on MARC coding the rules on how to catalog electronic resources are not discussed in depth.

Reproductions

Cataloging serial reproductions is not covered in this document. CONSER discusses them in Chapter 17 of the [CONSER Cataloging Manual](#).

[Intro](#) | [Resources](#) |

MARC Fields

[008](#) (Fixed Fields) | [022 041 042](#) (Numeric/Code Fields) | [100 110 111](#) (Main Entry Fields) | [130 240](#) (Uniform Title Fields) | [210 222 245 246 247](#) (Title Fields) | [250](#) (Edition Statement) | [260 300 310 321 362](#) (Descriptive Fields) | [440 490](#) (Series Fields) | [5xx \(General Comments\)](#) | [5xx's \(Major\)](#) | [5xx's \(Additional\)](#) | (Note Fields) | [6xx](#) (Subject Fields) | [700-711](#) (Name Added Entries) | [730-740](#) (Title Added Entries) | [76x-78x](#) (Linking Fields) | [8xx](#) (Series Added Entry and Holding Fields) |

008

Fixed Fields

Not all the codes in the 008 are discussed here.

See the following for additional information:

- [Use of Fixed Fields 006/007/008 and Leader Codes in CONSER Records](#),
- [Marc 21 Format for Bibliographic Data](#),
- [Bibliographic Formats and Standards](#).

Type "a" for textual material use "a" for electronic journals also	ELvl	Srcce	GPub	Ctrl	Lang	
BLvl "s" for Serial "i" is used for Integrating Resources	Form Form of item use "b" for microfiche use "a" for microfilm use "s" for electronic	Conf	Freq Current frequency See OCLC documentation for codes	MRec	Ctry	
S/L Successive or Latest Entry Cataloging Current practice is to use code 0 for Successive Entry	Orig	EntW	Regl "r" for published regularly. See OCLC documentation for other codes	Alph		
Desc	SrTp Type of Serial "p" for periodical "n" for newspaper See OCLC documentation for others.	Cont	DtSt Date Status "c" for currently published "d" for not current (dead)	Dates Based on the 362*	Date1 date of first issue (chronological designation on piece)*	Date2 date of last issue (chronological designation on piece)*

*These dates are taken from the 362 (first choice) and the 260 (second choice).

Be careful of mixed year pieces. The later of the years is always the one used.

Examples:

- For 1962-63 use 1963.
- For 1966-69 use 1969.

[Intro](#) | [Resources](#) |

MARC Fields

[008](#) (Fixed Fields) | [022](#) [041](#) [042](#) (Numeric/Code Fields) | [100](#) [110](#) [111](#) (Main Entry Fields) | [130](#) [240](#) (Uniform Title Fields) | [210](#) [222](#) [245](#) [246](#) [247](#) (Title Fields) | [250](#) (Edition Statement) | [260](#) [300](#) [310](#) [321](#) [362](#) (Descriptive Fields) | [440](#) [490](#) (Series Fields) | [5xx](#) (General Comments) | [5xx's \(Major\)](#) | [5xx's \(Additional\)](#) (Note Fields) | [6xx](#) (Subject Fields) | [700-711](#) (Name Added Entries) | [730-740](#) (Title Added Entries) | [76x-78x](#) (Linking Fields) | [8xx](#) (Series Added Entry and Holding Fields) | [84x-87x](#) (Holdings Fields) | [856](#) (Electronic Access) | [9xx](#) (Local Fields) |

022

ISSN (International Standard Serial Number)

Enter the ISSN in this field. ISSNs are *assigned* to titles by national ISSN centers. For more about ISSN, see [the U.S. ISSN website](#) or [the ISSN website](#).

Indicator 1

Level of international interest

Values

- blank=not specified
- 0=yes
- 1=no

Indicator 2

Undefined

Values are blank

Subfield a

Valid ISSN

- Transcribe ISSN found on piece.
- For e-journals, try to verify that the ISSN is not the print ISSN.

Subfield y

Incorrect ISSN

- Use if ISSN on piece is incorrect
 - Eg. Title has changed but new title still has previous ISSN on piece.
- Print ISSN is being used on online version of journal.
- If correcting the ISSN in a bib record, record the incorrect ISSN in subfield y.

Subfield z

Cancelled ISSN

Subfield 2

Source of ISSN

- Code 1 is for the U.S. ISSN Center at the NSDP (National Serials Data Program) located at LC.
- See [ISSN International Centre website](#) and [the US ISSN center website](#).

Example

- \$a 1934-5054 \$2 1
-

041

Language Code

CONSER Standard Record

- Code languages for serials with content in multiple languages.

- Subfield a is the only required subfield.
- If the information is only about translations, summaries, table of contents, or accompanying materials, then use a 564 note.

Language codes used can be found at: [MARC Code List for Languages](#)

Indicator 1

Translation indication

Values

- 0=Is not or does not contain a translation.
- 1=Is or contains a translation.

Indicator 2

Source of Code

Values

- blank=MARC language code.
- 7=Source specified in subfield 2.

Subfield a

Language code of text.

Repeatable.

Information on additional subfields can be found at [Marc 21 Format for Bibliographic Data.](#)

042

Authentication Code

- Code of cataloging authentication center that has created or reviewed the record.
- Used only by CONSER, LC, and PCC members.
- Do not add to records unless authorized.
- This code can help in choosing records.
- The codes can be found at: [MARC Code Lists for Relators, Sources, Description Conventions: Other Sources \(Field 042\)](#)

Indicators

Both indicators are undefined

Values are blank

Subfield a

Authentication Code

Codes to look for:

- lcd = CONSER records
- lc = Library of Congress
- nsdp = U.S. ISSN center

[Intro](#) | [Resources](#) |

MARC Fields

[008](#) (Fixed Fields) | [022 041 042](#) (Numeric/Code Fields) | [100 110 111](#) (Main Entry Fields) | [130 240](#) (Uniform Title Fields) | [210 222 245 246 247](#) (Title Fields) | [250](#) (Edition Statement) | [260 300 310 321 362](#) (Descriptive Fields) | [440 490](#) (Series Fields) | [5xx \(General Comments\)](#) | [5xx's \(Major\)](#) | [5xx's \(Additional\)](#) | (Note Fields) | [6xx](#) (Subject Fields) | [700-711](#) (Name Added Entries) | [730-740](#) (Title Added Entries) | [76x-78x](#) (Linking Fields) | [8xx](#) (Series Added Entry and Holding Fields) | [84x-87x](#) (Holdings Fields) | [856](#) (Electronic Access) | [9xx](#) (Local Fields) |

100

Main Entry--Personal Name

Rarely used in Serials. See LCRI 21.1A2 for usage.

Indicator 1

Type of Personal Name Entry

- 0=Forename
- 1=Surname
- 3=Family Name

Indicator 2

Undefined

Values are blank

Subfield a

Personal Name

Information on additional subfields can be found at [Marc 21 Format for Bibliographic Data](#).

110

Main Entry--Corporate Name

Used only when work emanates from the corporate body (Eg. annual report) not just when work published or sponsored by corporate body. See 21.B2 of [AACR2](#). If a conference name is subordinate to a corporate body it is entered as a 110.

Indicator 1

Type of Corporate Name Entry

- 0=Inverted Name
- 1=Jurisdiction Name
- 2=Name in Direct Order

Indicator 2

Undefined

Values are blank

Subfield a

Corporate Body

Examples

- 110 1# \$aTennessee. \$bDept. of Finance and Administration.
- 110 2# \$aTransportation Planning Capacity Building Program (U.S.)

Information on additional subfields can be found at [Marc 21 Format for Bibliographic Data](#).

111

Main Entry--Meeting Name

Used when a conference name is determined to be the Main Entry.

If a conference name is subordinate to a corporate body it is entered as a 110. Authorized (controlled) name headings should be used. See [Fritz](#), [AACR2](#), and [CONSER documentation](#).

Subfields are in this order a, n, p, d, c.

Make note of punctuation.

Indicator 1

Type of Meeting Name Entry

- 0=Inverted Name
- 1=Jurisdiction Name
- 2=Name in Direct Order

Indicator 2

Undefined

Values are blank

Subfield a

Meeting Name

Punctuation: Field ends in a period.

Subfield n

Number

Punctuation: Enclose text inside beginning parenthesis. Subfield on outside.

Subfield p

Name of part (Pre AACR2 only)

Subfield d

Date

Subfield c

Location

Punctuation: Fields ends with closed parenthesis.

Example

- 111 2_ \$a Southern Silvicultural Research Conference \$n (12th : \$d 2003 : \$c Biloxi, Miss.)
-

130

Uniform Title

The 130 is used differently for serials than for monographs. It serves to distinguish titles. It is mainly used to distinguish records for publications with the same title using qualifiers. Qualifiers such as place of publication, dates or format are used to create a distinguishing title.

CONSER Standard Record

Future use of the 130 will change with the implementation of the CONSER Standard Record.

- No longer required to distinguish titles except for generic titles like "Report."
- Still required for monographic series.
- [CONSER website](#)
- [CONSER Standard Record Documentation](#)
- [CONSER Standard Record Cheat Sheet](#)

Previous usage

Practices found in previously created records

- Used for a new record when a record already exists for a different publication with the same title.
 - American history (Westport, Conn.)
 - American history (Harrisburg, Pa.)
- Often used when a title reverts back to a former title or when a title is available online.

Atlantic monthly (Boston, Mass. : 1971)

- Journal of Japanese studies (Online)
- Used for series entries for monographic series
 - 130 00 Special report (National Research Council (U.S.). Transportation Research Board)
 - 245 10 Special report - Transportation Research Board, National Research Council.
- Not used for microform *versions* since these are reproductions not unique publications. Sometimes used for a *change* in physical medium. See 5.2.4 or the [CONSER Cataloging Manual](#)

Indicator 1

Non-filing characters

Number of character positions that represent articles (the, die, la) and should be ignored during indexing.

Values

- 0=No non-filing characters
- 1-9=Number of non-filing characters

Indicator 2

Undefined

Values are blank

Subfield a

Uniform Title

Title and qualifiers are all entered in subfield a.

See also:

[MARC 21 Format for Bibliographic Data \(Main Entries\)](#)

[MARC 21 Format for Bibliographic Data \(Uniform Titles\)](#)

[Intro](#) | [Resources](#) |

MARC Fields

[008](#) (Fixed Fields) | [022](#) [041](#) [042](#) (Numeric/Code Fields) | [100](#) [110](#) [111](#)(Main Entry Fields) | [130](#) [240](#) (Uniform Title Fields) | [210](#) [222](#) [245](#) [246](#) [247](#) (Title Fields) | [250](#) (Edition Statement) | [260](#) [300](#) [310](#) [321](#) [362](#) (Descriptive Fields) | [440](#) [490](#)(Series Fields) | [5xx](#) ([General Comments](#)) | [5xx's \(Major\)](#) | [5xx's \(Additional\)](#) | (Note Fields) | [6xx](#) (Subject Fields) | [700-711](#) (Name Added Entries) | [730-740](#) (Title Added Entries) | [76x-78x](#) (Linking Fields) | [8xx](#) (Series Added Entry and Holding Fields) | [84x-87x](#) (Holdings Fields) | [856](#) (Electronic Access) | [9xx](#) (Local Fields) |

210

Abbreviated Title

Supplied by ISSN center based on 222 (Key Title).

222

Key Title

Unique title linked to the ISSN. Assigned by ISSN centers only. Additional information can be found at [Marc 21 Format for Bibliographic Data](#).

240

Uniform Title

The 240 is used as a uniform title when a 1xx already exists in the record such as a corporate author.

Indicator 1

Uniform Title Printed or Displayed

Values

- 0=Not printed or displayed
- 1=Printed or displayed

Indicator 2

Non-filing characters

Number of character positions that represent articles (the, die, la) and should be ignored during indexing.

Values

- 0=No non-filing characters
- 1-9=Number of non-filing characters

Subfield a

Uniform Title

- Title and qualifiers are all entered in subfield a
 - Additional subfields can be found at [Marc 21 Format for Bibliographic Data](#).
-

245

Title Statement

This field is the standard 245 field. Remember with serials the 245 is taken from the first or earliest available issue. This information is tied to the [362](#). When not cataloged from the first issue, it is linked to a [500](#) note. Many serials do not have title pages. In such cases, source of title needs to be stated in a 500 note

Indicator 1

Added Entry

Values

- 0=No added entry
- 1=Added entry

Indicator 2

Non-filing characters

Number of character positions that represent articles (the, die, la) and should be ignored during indexing.

Values

- 0=No non-filing characters
- 1-9=Number of non-filing characters

Subfield a

Title

- \$a The daily news

Subfield b

Remainder of Title

CONSER Standard Record

- The CONSER standard record does not require subfield b unless it "provides clarification or support to the title proper that otherwise might appear misleading without the other title information." [CONSER Standard Record Documentation \(pg. 6\)](#)
 - Example:
 - \$b headlines to live by
- The transcription of parallel titles is also not required. However, the form not chosen as the title(s) proper must be recorded in separate 246's.

Initialism or acronyms are recorded in a 246 instead of a 245 subfield b

Subfield c

Statement of Responsibility

- \$c Proper Press

Additional subfields can be found at [Marc 21 Format for Bibliographic Data](#).

246

Varying Form of Title

- Used to record variant titles which may be used for searching.
- Also used to record minor title changes (use subfield f to record dates of change).
- Used to record acronyms and initialisms of the title proper instead of in the 245 subfield b.
- Used to record parallel titles.

Indicator 1

Note/Added Entry Controller

The term "Note" can be interpreted as "Displays in OPAC." The term "Added Entry" can be interpreted as "Indexed." If you want the title to be searchable, choose either 1 or 3. Be sure to test your local system to see how titles and notes display in the OPAC. See [Fritz](#) and the [CONSER Editing Guide](#).

Values

- 0=Note, No Added Entry
The title will display, but will not be indexed.
- 1=Note, Added Entry
The title will both display and be indexed.
- 2=No Note, No Added Entry
The title will not be displayed nor indexed.
- 3=No Note, Added Entry
The title will not display, but will be indexed.

Indicator 2

Type of Title

These values below (sometimes called "captions") may display in the OPAC. Be sure to test your local system. See also [Bibliographic Formats and Standards](#).

Values

- blank=No type specified. A free text statement is used instead. See subfield i
- 0=Portion of title. No note will be generated.
- 1=Parallel title. No note will be generated.
- 2=Distinctive title. Title on a specific issue. Use subfield f to identify which issue has this title.
- 3=Other title.
- 4=Cover title. Only use when the cover is not the chief source of description. Rare.
- 5=Added title page title. Title in another language on a title page that is not used as chief source. Rare.
- 6=Caption title. Title at the head of the first page of text when that is not the title in the 245.
- 7=Running title. Title printed at the top or bottom margin when that is not the title in the 245.
- 8=Spine title. Title printed by the publisher on the spine. Not the library's local binding title.

The most common subfields are listed below. See [Marc 21 Format for Bibliographic Data](#) or [Bibliographic Formats and Standards](#) for additional subfields.

Subfield a

Title proper

There are no non-filing indicators for the 246 field. When entering a varying title drop initial articles.

Subfield b
Remainder of title

Subfield f
Date or sequential designation

Used with second indicator 2 to indicate which title is involved.

Subfield i
Display text

If none of the other captions are appropriate, free text can be used with second indicator # . See [Bibliographic Formats and Standards](#) for additional information.

Examples

- 245 04 \$a The Bank of America journal of applied corporate finance.
246 1# \$i Issue for summer 1994 has title: \$a BankAmerica journal of applied corporate finance
- 245 00 \$a PPI detailed report / \$c U.S. Department of Labor, Bureau of Labor Statistics.
246 1# \$i Issue for Jan. 1997 has title: \$a Producer price indexes

Subfield n
Numbered part

Subfield p
Named part

Combination example

- 245 14 \$a The anatomical record. \$n Part B, \$p The new anatomist.
246 17 \$a Anatomical record. \$n Part B, \$p New anat. \$f <2005-2006>

247

Former Title

It should not be used with Successive Entry cataloging of Serials. Previously the 247 was used under Latest Entry cataloging of serials. The 245 was updated as titles changed. The 247 field can currently be used for Integrating Resources. See [CONSER website](#) for more information about Integrating Resources.

250

Edition Statement

For Serials the edition statement is used to distinguish different editions of the entire serial run such geographic, interest groups, formats, or languages. Examples: a Student's edition from a Teacher's edition or the North American edition from the South American edition.

Statements such as "1st edition" generally are recorded as enumeration in the 362.

Indicators
Both indicators are undefined

Values are blank

Subfield a
Edition statement

Subfield b
Remainder of edition statement

260

Publication, distribution etc.

CONSER Standard Record practices are described.

Indicator 1

Sequence of publishing statements

Values are not yet implemented

Indicator 2

Undefined

Values are blank

Subfield a

Place of publication, distribution, etc.

- The CONSER Standard Record requires only that the first named place of publication be supplied in subfield a.
- This does not change depending on the home country of cataloging agency.
- For online resources if the place of publication is available in the first few pages of the home page, record in the 260 subfield a. If not, supply a probably place of publication in brackets or use [S.I.].

Subfield b

Name of publisher

Note: records created before 2002 may have a comma following the publisher name and before a non-existent subfield c, as this was the practice when cataloging was done without the first or last issue in hand.

Subfield c

Date of publication

Dates are not required to be supplied by originally created CONSER Standard Records. See the [362](#) field for more information about dates.

[Intro](#) | [Resources](#) |

MARC Fields

[008](#) (Fixed Fields) | [022 041 042](#) (Numeric/Code Fields) | [100 110 111](#) (Main Entry Fields) | [130 240](#) (Uniform Title Fields) | [210 222 245 246 247](#) (Title Fields) | [250](#) (Edition Statement) | [260 300 310 321 362](#) (Descriptive Fields) | [440 490](#) (Series Fields) | [5xx \(General Comments\)](#) | [5xx's \(Major\)](#) | [5xx's \(Additional\)](#) | (Note Fields) | [6xx](#) (Subject Fields) | [700-711](#) (Name Added Entries) | [730-740](#) (Title Added Entries) | [76x-78x](#) (Linking Fields) | [8xx](#) (Series Added Entry and Holding Fields) | [84x-87x](#) (Holdings Fields) | [856](#) (Electronic Access) | [9xx](#) (Local Fields) |

300

Physical Description

- Extent of the item, illustration, dimensions, and accompanying material.
- Only subfield "a" differs for serials.
- The other subfields must cover the *entire run* of the title.

CONSER Standard Record

- CONSER Standard Record requires subfield a only for *tangible non-print* formats.
- CONSER Standard Record does not require subfield b or c.

Indicators

Both indicators are undefined

Values are blank

Subfield a

Extent of item

Non-completed titles (publication ongoing)

- Use appropriate smd (special material designator)
 - smd examples: v. no. pt.
- Do not use specific numbers since total is not known until title ceases.
 - Example: \$a v., \$b

Completed titles (ceased titles)

- Use appropriate smd (special material designator)
- Show number of bibliographic units for the title.
- Do not indicate how they were bound locally, but how many units were published.
 - \$a 20 v., \$b
 - \$a 12 pt.

Subfield b

Other physical details

Such as illustrations, maps etc.

Subfield c

Dimensions

310

Current Publication Frequency

This is tied to the fixed field [Freq.](#)

Indicators

Both indicators are undefined

Values are blank

Subfield a

Current Frequency

If no 321, spell out the number, if one or more 321's then use numbers

- \$a Three issues yearly

Subfield b

Date of current frequency

- Only used when a 321 exists and if the date of frequency is different from beginning date of publication.
 - Subfield preceded by a comma.
 - Angle brackets <..> mean that the date within the brackets is the first known date, prior dates are uncertain.
 - \$a Three times yearly, \$b 1932-
 - \$a Ten times a year, \$b <Apr. 1992> -
-

321

Former Publication Frequency

CONSER Standard Record

- CONSER Standard Record does not require for Original/New records.
- Do not remove from existing records.

Indicators

Both indicators are undefined

Values are blank

Subfield a

Former Frequency

- Use only if a 310 exists
- Earliest is first (top) one
- Spell out number in first 321
 - \$a Four issues yearly
- If more than three 321's use "Frequency varies".
 - 321 \$a Frequency varies

Subfield b

Former Frequency Dates

- Required in all 321 fields
- Input is similar to the 310 field.
 - \$a Three times yearly, **\$b 1932-1939**
- Angle brackets <..> mean that the date within the bracket is the earliest or latest known date; other dates are uncertain.
 - \$a Ten times a year, **\$b 1990-<Apr. 1992>**
 - \$a Ten times a year, **\$b <Apr. 1992>-1999**

362

Dates of publication or sequential designation

Beginning and/or ending designations of the run of the title. Shows the run of the title, NOT local holdings, and not usually publication dates, which are in the 260. There are two ways this information can be represented: Formatted and Unformatted. The first indicator is used to code the style used.

Indicator 1

Format of Date

Prior to the CONSER Standard Record dates were entered as Formatted or Unformatted. A record may have one of each, but not two of the same style.

CONSER Standard Record

The CONSER Standard Record practice is to always use the Unformatted style. See [CONSER Standard Record Documentation](#).

Values

- 0=Formatted style
 - Designations in a specific style
 - [Marc 21 Format for Bibliographic Data](#) has examples.
 - Must have 1st or last issue in hand, when doing original cataloging.
 - If first part is a smd (special material designator) the first letter is capitalized
 - volume is Vol.
 - Formatted, the title is ongoing
 - Vol. 1, no. 1 (Jan. 2000) -
 - Formatted, the title is complete. The smd is abbreviated v. etc. Use month abbreviations from AACR2
 - Vol. 1, no. 1 (Jan. 2000) - v.2, no.4 (Sept. 2001)
- 1=Unformatted style

Not repeatable. Combine begin and end dates if necessary.

- Free text is used.
- Supplies numbering/dates whether or not the first issue is in hand.
- Examples:
 - Began with v.1 (Spring 2007).
 - Began with v. 3?
 - Ends with issue 100.
 - Began with v.10 (1970); ceased with v.20 (1980).
- Captions and months may be transcribed as found, or they may use standard AACR2 abbreviations.
- Numbers can be transcribed or recorded as Arabic numerals.
- If numbering is not present or known, use publication or copyright date.
- If numbering has dates and issue numbers, surround date with parentheses.
- New series designations can be in this field or the 515, whichever is clearer.
- Entered with first indicator code 1.

Indicator 2
Undefined

Values are blank

Subfield a
Dates of publication or sequential designation

Enter publication designations here. Use parentheses for chronological information if given in addition to sequential designations. See [Marc 21 Format for Bibliographic Data](#).

[Intro](#) | [Resources](#) |

MARC Fields

[008](#) (Fixed Fields) | [022 041 042](#) (Numeric/Code Fields) | [100 110 111](#) (Main Entry Fields) | [130 240](#) (Uniform Title Fields) | [210 222 245 246 247](#) (Title Fields) | [250](#) (Edition Statement) | [260 300 310 321 362](#) (Descriptive Fields) | [440 490](#) (Series Fields) | [5xx \(General Comments\)](#) | [5xx's \(Major\)](#) | [5xx's \(Additional\)](#) | (Note Fields) | [6xx](#) (Subject Fields) | [700-711](#) (Name Added Entries) | [730-740](#) (Title Added Entries) | [76x-78x](#) (Linking Fields) | [8xx](#) (Series Added Entry and Holding Fields) | [84x-87x](#) (Holdings Fields) | [856](#) (Electronic Access) | [9xx](#) (Local Fields) |

440

Series Statement/Added Title Entry

Note: use of this field may be changing with new Marbi standards.

Used when the series statement transcribed from the piece is the same as the authorized form of the heading. No corresponding 8xx is necessary.

- 400, 410, and 411 are no longer valid.
- Do not use numbering if it changes with each issue/volume. It is used if it stays the same with each issue.
- Input subfields in the following order a, n, p, x, v.

CONSER Standard Record

Transcription is not required if a series authority record exists or is being established.

If a series authority record exists:

- Use only the 8xx field to trace the series.
 - (Exception: use 490 if need to record ISSN for series.)
- Variant forms of the series title are recorded in the authority record.

If no series authority record exists or is being created

- Use the 490.
- Document changes to series statement in 490.

See [CONSER Standard Record Documentation](#) for more information.

Indicator 1

Undefined

Values are blank

Indicator 2

Non-filing characters

Number of character positions that represent articles (the, die, la) and should be ignored during indexing.

Values

- 0=No non-filing characters
- 1-9=Number of non-filing characters

Subfield a

Title excluding numbering and part name

- \$a Journal of urban studies

Subfield n

Number of part/section of work

Usually a subseries, which goes with the part in subfield p.

- \$n Part B

Subfield p

Name of part/section of work

- \$p Cities

Subfield v

Volume number/sequential designation

- \$v v.2

Subfield x

ISSN

- \$x xxxx-xxxx
-

490

Series statement

Note: use of this field may be changing with new Marbi standards.

Series statement where the series is not traced, or is traced in a different form from what is on the piece, but is not a major title change for the series title.

- The 490 is what is on the piece and the 8xx is the official traced form.
- Input in the following order a,x,v

CONSER Standard Record

- Use only if no series authority record exists. (No 8xx fields.)
- Exception: use 490 if needed to record ISSN for series.
- Document changes to series statement over time in 490.

See [CONSER Standard Record Documentation](#) for more information.

Indicator 1

States whether the series is traced or not.

Values

- 0=Series not traced
- 1=Series traced differently

Indicator 2
Undefined

Values are blank

Subfield a
Series statement

- \$a Family bulletin

Subfield x
ISSN

- \$x xxxx-xxxx

Subfield v
Volume number/sequential designation

- \$v v.4

[Intro](#) | [Resources](#) |

MARC Fields

[008](#) (Fixed Fields) | [022](#) [041](#) [042](#) (Numeric/Code Fields) | [100](#) [110](#) [111](#) (Main Entry Fields) | [130](#) [240](#) (Uniform Title Fields) | [210](#) [222](#) [245](#) [246](#) [247](#) (Title Fields) | [250](#) (Edition Statement) | [260](#) [300](#) [310](#) [321](#) [362](#) (Descriptive Fields) | [440](#) [490](#) (Series Fields) | [5xx](#) ([General Comments](#)) | [5xx's \(Major\)](#) | [5xx's \(Additional\)](#) | (Note Fields) | [6xx](#) (Subject Fields) | [700-711](#) (Name Added Entries) | [730-740](#) (Title Added Entries) | [76x-78x](#) (Linking Fields) | [8xx](#) (Series Added Entry and Holding Fields) | [84x-87x](#) (Holdings Fields) | [856](#) (Electronic Access) | [9xx](#) (Local Fields) |

5xx

General Comments

Order of Note fields: according to CONSER practices 5xx notes are arranged in tag order except for 533 and 539, which follow all other 5xx notes. [Notes for Serials Cataloging](#) is an excellent source for many examples of serials notes, especially wording variations. See the [CONSER Editing Guide](#) for further examples.

The Note fields have been grouped into Major fields and Additional fields below.

Major Note fields

[500](#) [510](#) [515](#) [525](#) [530](#) [533](#) [538](#) [546](#) [550](#) [580](#) [590](#) [Additional 5xx Fields](#)

500

General Note

CONSER Standard Record

CONSER Standard Record requires the following on all records:

- Description Based on Note
 - When based on the first issue, this note is given as "Description based on the first issue."
- Source of Title Note
- Latest Issue Consulted Note (when appropriate.)
- The Description Based on Note and the Source of Title Note can be combined in one field.

Indicators
Both indicators are undefined

Values are blank

Subfield a

General Note

These are the major uses of a General Note. See the [CONSER documentation](#) for more.

- Source of title note
Indicates where the title was taken from if there is no title page, may be combined with the description based on note (see below) when it is present.
 - \$a Title from caption
 - \$a Description based on v.6, no.2 (Jan. 2000); title from cover.
- Other title information
Can be used for unique titles
 - \$a Each volume has a distinctive title.
- Publisher changes
Use for changes in commercial publisher, changes in issuing body are coded as a 550 note. When three or more occur use publisher varies notes.
 - \$a Published: Seattle :
 - \$a Publisher varies
- Description based on note
Use in all records. Previously used when the description was based on an issue other than the first. Is combined with the source of title note when both are present.
 - \$a Description based on v. 10, no. 1 (Feb. 1997).
- Latest issue consulted
 - Example: \$a Latest issue consulted: 33rd 2007.
 - Use when the information in the record is NOT based on the same issue as that in the description based on note.
 - Record must include most current frequency and publisher information as of the issue cited in the latest issue consulted. It may include source of acquisition information.
 - Often used when record is edited with up-to-date information.
 - **CONSER Standard Record**
 - CONSER Standard Record allows use with the final issue, eg. "Final issue consulted."
 - Previously this was in a 936 with acronym LIC.

510

Citation/Reference Notes

Obsolete.

Previously used to specify where an item had been reviewed, indexed or cited. Chemical abstracts information is still maintained and some rare serial information still exists in serial records.

515

Numbering peculiarities note

Used to show irregularities or peculiarities in publication numbering or patterns, report year coverage, or issued in parts information.

Indicators

Both indicators are undefined

Values are blank

Subfield a

Numbering peculiarities note

- \$a Vol. 6, no.10 not published.

- \$a Some issues lack volume numbering.
 - \$a Issued in parts.
 - \$a Report covers two fiscal years.
-

530

Additional physical form available note

Indicates the presence of a reproduction or a related version or format. If a linking entry is paired with this note, use the [776](#).

Indicators

Both indicators are undefined

Values are blank

Subfield a

Additional physical form available

- \$a Also available in microfilm.
- \$a Also available in print.

Subfield u

Uniform resource locator

Example

- \$u <http://jama.ama-assn.org/>

Usually URL is entered in the 856 field, subfield u instead of 530.

533

Reproduction Note

A note used when the item cataloged is a reproduction of an original item. The description in the body of the record is of the original and characteristics of reproduction are recorded in the 533 note. Commonly used for microforms. Fixed field tag "Form of item" and an 007 should also be coded for the reproduction, not the original. See [Use of fixed fields 006/007/008 and leader codes in CONSER records](#) for more information. Subfields a and b are mandatory. Subfields are input in the following order a,m,b,c,d,e,f,n,6,7

Indicators

Both indicators are undefined

Values are blank

Subfield a

Type of reproduction

Mandatory subfield.

- \$a Microfilm.
- \$a Photocopy.

Subfield b

Place of reproduction

Mandatory subfield.

- \$b Ann Arbor, Mich. :

Subfield c

Agency responsible for the reproduction

- \$c Vatican Archives

Subfield d

Date of reproduction

For serials, the beginning and ending dates of publication for the serial, preceding punctuation varies depending on whether this field is included.

- \$d 2000

Subfield e

Physical description of reproduction

For serials, include the number of fiche or film if it is complete

- \$e 30 microfiches.

Subfield f

Series statement of reproduction

Series that the reproduction belongs to, enclosed in parentheses. Use an 8xx if appropriate.

Subfield m

Dates/sequential designation of issues reproduced

Primarily for preservation masters, optional for the rest. See [CONSER documentation](#) for more details.

Subfield n

Note about reproduction

Subfield 3

Materials specified

538

System Details Note

Used for recording system requirements and mode of access notes for direct and remote access computer serials and videorecordings.

CONSER Standard Record

- CONSER Standard Record does not require a 538 note for direct access serials unless it is necessary to indicate the type of operating system or make and model of computer for which the the resource was designed.
- For remote access serials only use if the resource is not accessed via the World Wide Web.

Indicators

Both indicators are undefined

Values are blank

Subfield a

System details note

Subfield a

Uniform resource locator

- \$a Systems requirements: Pentium III or higher computer.
- \$a Mode of access: Available via FTP

Subfield i

Display text

Allows for the display of specific text indicated by the i.

- \$i Selection of the:

Subfield u

Uniform resource locator

Subfield 3

Materials specified

546

Language Note

CONSER Standard Record

- CONSER Standard Record provides that if the main content is in more than one language use an 041 and only use subfield a.
- If the language information is about translations, summaries, table of contents, or accompanying material language differences, record in a 546.
- Paired with the [041](#) field and the fixed field [Lang](#) code.

Indicators

Both indicators are undefined

Values are blank

Subfield a

Language Note

- \$a Text in English and German

Subfield b

Information code or alphabet

Name of the script or code used. Not used if it is embedded in the subfield a information

- \$b Hebrew Alphabet

Subfield 3

Materials specified

Materials to which the language code applies

550

Issuing Body Note

Note about former and current issuing bodies that are usually traced in a 710. Current issuing bodies are only included when not part of the title, or statement of responsibility. Includes notes about translating, editing, and compiling. Also for notes stating the title is and official publication of the issuing body. Commercial publisher changes are noted in a 500 note.

CONSER Standard Record

CONSER Standard Record does not require the use of a 550 or other notes to justify added entries.

Indicators

Both indicators are undefined

Values are blank

Subfield a

Issuing body note

- \$a Vols. For 2000- issued by the University of Memphis.
-

580

Linking Complexity Note

Note describing relationships too complex for standard display constants in 7xx linking notes. Does not replace the 7xx except in special cases noted in the MARC documentation.

CONSER Standard Record

CONSER Standard Record does not require information in this field. Preferred use is subfield i in a linking note.

Indicators

Both indicators are undefined

Values are blank

Subfield a

Linking complexity note

- \$a Merged with title X to form title Y.
-

590

Local Note

For local or library specific notes to be used in local system. Do not add to records in the OCLC database.

[Additional Note fields](#)

[504 511 513 516 520 521 522 534 535 536 539 547 555 556 583 Major 5xx's](#)

[Skip to Other MARC Fields](#)

504

Bibliography, etc. note

For serials this is used only for important bibliographies or discographies.

Indicators

Both indicators are undefined

Values are blank

Subfield a

Bibliography, etc. note

- \$a Each volume includes a bibliography.
-

511

Participant/Performer

Note about participants and performers, for serials is usually only for video recordings and sound recordings.

Indicator 1

Display constant controller

Values

- blank=No information provided Obsolete
- 0=No display constant generated
- 1=Cast
- 2=Presenter Obsolete
- 3=Narrator Obsolete

Indicator 2

Undefined

Values are blank

513

Type of Report and Period Covered Note

Gives the type of report and the period it covers. Usually only subfield a is used.

Indicators

Both indicators are undefined

Values are blank

Subfield a

Type of report

- \$a Annual report

Subfield b

Period covered

Used only if the report is complete in one issue

- \$b September 1996 - August 1997
-

516

Type of Computer File or Data Note

Note characterizes the computer file aspects of the title. Includes both general descriptors (such as "text") and specific information (such as "hypertext".)

Indicator 1

Display constant controller (generates the text displayed by system)

Values

- blank=Type of file - generates "Type of file" display
- 0=8 no display constant generated

Indicator 2

Undefined

Values are blank

Subfield a

Entire text of the note

- \$a Text and graphic.
-

520

Summary etc.

Note that describes the scope and contents of the material. In serials cataloging used only for notes that are preceded by the display constant "Summary."

Indicator 1

Display constant controller (generates the text displayed by system)

Values

- blank=Summary
- 0=Subject
- 1=Review
- 2=Scope and content
- 3=Abstract
- 8=No display constant generated

Indicator 2

Undefined

Values are blank

Subfield a

Text of the summary

- \$a Directory of institutions working in the field of

Subfield u

Subfield u url of summary

CONSER does not use if 856 field is used.

521

Target audience note

Note that describes the intended audience of the serial. CONSER only uses quoted notes and specified indicators.

Indicator 1

Display constant controller

Values

- # (blank), 0, 1, 2, 3, 4 NOT used in CONSER records
- 8=No display constant generated

Indicator 2

Undefined

Values are blank

Subfield a

Entire note in quotation marks

- \$a "For teachers in secondary schools"
-

522

Geographic coverage

Records the geographic coverage of the serial, most often used with survey material. This information is also

coded in the 052.

Indicator 1

Display constant controller

Values

- blank=Geographic coverage
- 8=No display constant generated

Indicator 2

Undefined

Values are blank

Subfield a

Entire text of the note

- \$a Southeastern United States.
-

525

Supplement note

Used for supplements that are not cataloged on separate bibliographic records. See [770](#) or [772](#) field for supplements that are cataloged separately. See [CONSER Editing Guide](#).

Indicators

Both indicators are undefined

Values are blank

Subfield a

Supplement note

- \$a Supplements accompany some volumes.
 - \$a Volumes kept up to day by midyear supplements.
-

534

Original version note

Used by the Library and Archives of Canada.

535

Location of Originals/Duplicates Note

Used to record the name and address of the repository which controls the originals or duplicates of the materials described, if the repository is different from where the materials are held.

Indicator 1

Custodial Role

Values

- 1=Holder of originals
- 2=Holder of duplicates

Indicator 2

Undefined

Values are blank

Subfield a
Custodian

536 Funding Information

Note which includes numbers associated with funded projects.

Indicators
Both indicators are undefined

Values are blank

Subfield a
Text of note

539 Fixed-Length Data Elements of Reproduction

OCLC note field. Paired with the [533](#) and encodes in OCLC the fixed field information that is described in the 533. In OCLC used instead of 533 subfield 7. See [Bibliographic Formats and Standards](#) for more information.

Indicators
Both indicators are undefined

Values are blank

See [Bibliographic Formats and Standards](#) for subfield information.

547 Former Title Complexity Note

Note is used only when 247's exist in a record. Is used when the 247 relationships are too complex to be understood just by the use of the [247](#). These are only used in older serial records using latest entry cataloging or current integrating resource records, but never in successive entry serial records.

Indicator 1
Undefined

Values are blank

Indicator 2
Undefined

Values are blank

Subfield a
Former title complexity note

- \$a Title varies: 1920-1922, title 1-1923-1925, title 2.
-

555 Cumulative Index/Finding Aids Note

A note indicating the volumes and or dates of indexes or finding aids *specific* to this title and whether it is

included with the serial or must be purchased separately. This does not include indexing and/or abstracting resources for this title.

Indicator 1

Display constant controller

Values

- blank=Indexes
- 0=Finding aids (not used for serials)
- 8=No display constant generated

Indicator 2

Undefined

Values are blank

Subfield a

Cumulate index/finding aids note

- \$a Vols. 1-10 in volume 10.
-

556

Information About Documentation Note

Note used to record the documentation about the contents or use of the serial.

Indicator 1

Display constant controller

Values

- blank=Documentation
- 8=No display constant generated

Indicator 2

Undefined

Values are blank

Subfield a

Information about documentation note

- \$a Accompanied by manual on how to use the product.
- \$a Users guide available on the World Wide Web.

Subfield z

ISBN association with the document.

583

Action Note

Note which shows action to be taken on the materials listed, such as preservation or microfilming.

Indicator 1

Privacy

Values

- blank=No information provided
- 0=Private

- 1=Not private

Indicator 2

Undefined

Values are blank

Subfield a

Action

- \$a Preserve

Other subfields are used as needed about the action. See [MARC documentation](#).

[Intro](#) | [Resources](#) |

MARC Fields

[008](#) (Fixed Fields) | [022 041 042](#) (Numeric/Code Fields) | [100 110 111](#) (Main Entry Fields) | [130 240](#) (Uniform Title Fields) | [210 222 245 246 247](#) (Title Fields) | [250](#) (Edition Statement) | [260 300 310 321 362](#) (Descriptive Fields) | [440 490](#) (Series Fields) | [5xx \(General Comments\)](#) | [5xx's \(Major\)](#) | [5xx's \(Additional\)](#) | (Note Fields) | [6xx](#) (Subject Fields) | [700-711](#) (Name Added Entries) | [730-740](#) (Title Added Entries) | [76x-78x](#) (Linking Fields) | [8xx](#) (Series Added Entry and Holding Fields) | [84x-87x](#) (Holdings Fields) | [856](#) (Electronic Access) | [9xx](#) (Local Fields) |

6xx

Subject headings

Only the differences in Subject Fields usage for Serials are discussed here.

The major differences are in the use of the subfield v and x for Periodicals.

For additional information on indicator and subfield use, see the [Marc 21 Format for Bibliographic Data](#) or Bibliographic Formats and Standards.

Subfield v

Form subdivision

Form subdivisions indicate what something *is* as opposed to what it is *about*. So the form is used when the title is a periodical as defined in H 1927 of the [Subject Cataloging Manual](#). It is usually the last subdivision in the string.

- \$v Periodicals

Subfield x

General subdivision

This subfield is used when the title is about periodicals, such as Ulrich's.

- \$x Periodicals

[Intro](#) | [Resources](#) |

MARC Fields

[008](#) (Fixed Fields) | [022 041 042](#) (Numeric/Code Fields) | [100 110 111](#) (Main Entry Fields) | [130 240](#) (Uniform Title Fields) | [210 222 245 246 247](#) (Title Fields) | [250](#) (Edition Statement) | [260 300 310 321 362](#) (Descriptive Fields) | [440 490](#) (Series Fields) | [5xx \(General Comments\)](#) | [5xx's \(Major\)](#) | [5xx's \(Additional\)](#) | (Note Fields) | [6xx](#) (Subject Fields) | [700-711](#) (Name Added Entries) | [730-740](#) (Title Added Entries) | [76x-78x](#) (Linking Fields) | [8xx](#) (Series Added Entry and Holding Fields) | [84x-87x](#) (Holdings Fields) | [856](#) (Electronic Access) | [9xx](#) (Local Fields) |

700

Added Entry--Personal Name

Very rarely used in Serials. Usually only for editors or those responsible for issuing the serial.

Indicator 1

Type of Personal Name Entry

- 0=Forename
- 1=Surname
- 3=Family Name

Indicator 2

Type of Added Entry

- blank=No information provided
- 2=Analytical

Subfield a

Personal Name

Information on additional subfields can be found at [Marc 21 Format for Bibliographic Data.](#)

710

Added Entry--Corporate Name

If a conference name is subordinate to a corporate body it is entered as a 710.

Indicator 1

Type of Corporate Name Entry

- 0=Inverted Name
- 1=Jurisdiction Name
- 2=Name in Direct Order

Indicator 2

Type of Added Entry

- blank=No information provided
- 2=Analytical

Subfield a

Corporate Body

Information on additional subfields can be found at [field 110](#) or [Marc 21 Format for Bibliographic Data.](#)

711

Added Entry--Meeting Name

If a conference name is subordinate to a corporate body it is entered as a 710.

Indicator 1

Type of Meeting Name Entry

- 0=Inverted Name
- 1=Jurisdiction Name
- 2=Name in Direct Order

Indicator 2

Type of Added Entry

- blank=No information provided
- 2=Analytical

Information on subfields can be found at [field 111](#) or [Marc 21 Format for Bibliographic Data.](#)

Title Added Entries

Use as additional title access points. Use a 730 when the added entry title appears in another bibliographic record or the name authority file. If the title does not appear in either, use a 740. In a 730, use the main entry form from the other record. Linking entries do not replace added entries. See [AACR2](#).

CONSER Standard Record

CONSER Standard Record practice gives preference to linking entries and does not require added entries that would duplicate linking entries, except for translations and language editions. See [CONSER Documentation](#) for more information.

730

Added Entry - Uniform Title

If a title does not exist in another bibliographic record, or have an authority record, use a 740.

CONSER Standard Record

CONSER Standard Record does not require added entries that would duplicate linking entries, except for translations and language editions. See [Title Added Entries](#).

Indicator 1

Non-filing characters

Number of character positions that represent articles (the, die, la) and should be ignored during indexing.

Values are 0-9

Indicator 2

Type of Added Entry

- blank=No information provided
- 2=Analytical

Subfield a

Uniform Title

Title and qualifiers are all entered in subfield a.

Subfield h

Medium

Media qualifier. Do not use.

Information on additional subfields can be found at [Marc 21 Format for Bibliographic Data](#).

740

Added Entry - Uncontrolled Related/Analytical Title

If the title has an authority record or exists in another bibliographic record, use the 730 field.

CONSER Standard Record

CONSER Standard Record does not require added entries that would duplicate linking entries, except for translations and language editions. See [Title Added Entries](#).

Indicator 1

Non-filing characters

Number of character positions that represent articles (the, die, la) and should be ignored during indexing.

Values are 0-9

Indicator 2

Type of Added Entry

- blank=No information provided
- 0=Alternative entry
- 1=Secondary entry/Added entry printed on LC cards
- 2=Analytical
- 3=Added entry not printed on LC cards

Subfield a

Uncontrolled related/analytical title

Title and qualifiers are all entered in subfield a.

Information on additional subfields can be found at [Marc 21 Format for Bibliographic Data](#).

[Intro](#) | [Resources](#) |

MARC Fields

[008](#) (Fixed Fields) | [022 041 042](#) (Numeric/Code Fields) | [100 110 111](#)(Main Entry Fields) | [130 240](#) (Uniform Title Fields) | [210 222 245 246 247](#) (Title Fields) | [250](#) (Edition Statement) | [260 300 310 321 362](#) (Descriptive Fields) | [440 490](#)(Series Fields) | [5xx \(General Comments\)](#) | [5xx's \(Major\)](#) | [5xx's \(Additional\)](#) | (Note Fields) | [6xx](#) (Subject Fields) | [700-711](#) (Name Added Entries) | [730-740](#) (Title Added Entries) | [76x-78x](#) (Linking Fields) | [8xx](#) (Series Added Entry and Holding Fields) | [84x-87x](#) (Holdings Fields) | [856](#) (Electronic Access) | [9xx](#) (Local Fields) |

76x-78x

Linking entries

A Linking Entry is a field which describes and links to another title, which usually has its own record. Records can be linked to former titles which do not have bibliographic records.

CONSER Standard Record

Linking entries do not replace added entries. See [AACR2](#). However, CONSER Standard Record practice gives preference to linking entries and does not require added entries that would duplicate linking entries, except for translations and language editions. See [CONSER documentation](#).

The most common Linking Fields used in Serials are described below. See the [MARC documentation](#) for information on fields 760, 762, 765, 767, 775, 777, 786 to determine which may be used and their order.

[770](#) [772](#) [773](#) [774](#) [776](#) [780](#) [785](#) [787](#)

770

Supplement Special/Issue Entry

Record in this field a supplement or a special issue to the title in the 245. This field is paired with the [772](#) Parent Entry field. This can be considered to be a child entry to the title in the 245.

Indicator 1

Note controller

Values

- 0=Display note
- 1=Do not display note

Indicator 2

Display constant controller

Values

- #=Has supplement
- 8=No display constant generated

For the subfields see the [780 subfields](#).

772 Supplement parent entry

Record in this field the parent entry to the title in the 245. In other words, the title in the 245 of the record being worked on is the supplement of the 772 title. This field is paired with the [770](#) Supplement/special issue field.

Indicator 1
Note controller

Values

- 0=Display note
- 1=Do not display note

Indicator 2
Display constant controller

Values

- #=Supplement to
- 0=Parent
- 8=No display constant generated

For the subfields see the [780 subfields](#).

773 Host Item Entry

If the title being cataloged (the title in the 245 field) is a constituent unit (part of a larger unit), use this field to record the host item. Used only if the bibl level is set to b. This field is paired with the [774](#) Constituent Unit Entry.

Indicator 1
Note controller

Values

- 0=Display note
- 1=Do not display note

Indicator 2
Display constant controller

Values

- #=In
- 8=No display constant generated

For the subfields see the [780 subfields](#).

774 Constituent Unit Entry

Used to record a constituent unit of the title being cataloged (the title in the 245 field). This field is paired with

the [773](#) Host Item Entry.

Indicator 1

Note controller

Values

- 0=Display note
- 1=Do not display note

Indicator 2

Display constant controller

Values

- #=Constituent unit
- 8=No display constant generated

For the subfields see the [780 subfields](#).

776

Additional Physical Form

Used to link records for other physical forms of the title, such as microforms, or electronic resources.

Indicator 1

Note controller

Values

- 0=Display note
- 1=Do not display note

Indicator 2

Display constant controller

Values

- #=Issued in another form
- 8=No display constant generated

For the subfields see the [780 subfields](#).

780

Preceding Title

Used to record the title(s) just prior to the title being cataloged. The nature of the relationship is recorded using the indicators and/or the 580 field. There may be more than one 780 in a record when complex relationships exist, such as splits and mergers.

Indicator 1

Note Controller

Values

- 0=Display
- 1=Do Not Display (use 580 note instead)

Be sure to test your local system to see how titles and notes display in the OPAC

Indicator 2

Type of relationship

Values below can display in OPAC

Values

- 0=Continues
- 1=Continues in part
- 2=Supercedes (No longer used)
- 3=Supercedes in part (No longer used)
- 4=Formed by the union of ... and ...

Two or more 780's would be used depending on the number of titles involved:

- 580 Formed by the union of: DePaul business law journal and: Commercial law journal.
- 780 14 †† DePaul business law journal
- 780 14 †† Commercial law journal
- 5=Absorbed
- 6=Absorbed in part
- 7=Separated from

Subfields

The most common subfields are listed below according to input order. Most linking entries will have subfield t, subfield x and subfield w.

Example: †† DePaul business law journal †x 1049-6122 †w (DLC) 90655044 †w (OCoLC)20064809

Additional information can be found at [Marc 21 Format for Bibliographic Data](#). See the [CONSER Editing Guide](#) for subfield input order. See OCLC's [Bibliographic Formats and Standards](#) for subfield w input standards.

Subfield a

Main Entry

If preceding title has a name main entry it is entered here. See [Bibliographic Formats and Standards](#) for more information.

Subfield s

Uniform Title

If preceding title has a 240, it is entered here. See [Bibliographic Formats and Standards](#) for more information.

Subfield t

Title

Title from 245 is entered here. Be sure to test your local ILS to see how it handles the various subfields.

Subfield x

ISSN number

Subfield w

Record control number

Usually the LCCN number and the OCLC number are entered. OCLC has an input standard for subfield w. See OCLC's website, 7XX fields: [Bibliographic Formats and Standards](#).

Examples

- †w (DLC)sn 90033532
- †w (DLC) 44003576
- †w (OCoLC)5295621

785

Succeeding Title

Used to record the title(s) immediately following the one being cataloged. The nature of the relationship is recorded using the indicators and/or the 580 field. There may be more than one 785 in a record when complex relationships exist, such as splits and mergers.

Indicator 1

Note Controller

Values

- 0=Display
- 1=Do Not Display (use [580](#) note instead)

Be sure to test your local system to see how titles and notes display in the OPAC

Indicator 2

Type of relationship

Values below can display in OPAC

Values

- 0=Continued by
- 1=Continued in part by
- 2=Superseded by (No longer used)
- 3=Superseded in part by (No longer used)
- 4=Absorbed by
- 5=Absorbed in part by
- 6=Split into ... and ...

Two or more 785's would be used depending on the number of titles involved:

- 580 Split into: Anatomical record. Part A, Discoveries in molecular, cellular, and evolutionary biology; and Anatomical record. Part B, New anatomist.
- 785 16 †† Anatomical record. Part A, Discoveries in molecular, cellular, and evolutionary biology
- 785 16 †† Anatomical record. Part B, New anatomist
- 7=Merged with ... to form ...

Two or more 785's would be used depending on the number of titles involved:

- 580 Merged with: Instructor (Intermediate edition), to form: Instructor (New York, N.Y. : 1999).
- 785 17 †† Instructor (Intermediate edition)
- 785 17 †† Instructor (New York, N.Y. : 1999)
- 8=Changed back to

For the subfields see the 780 field. [780 Subfields](#)

787

Nonspecific relationship

Used when none of the defined fields is appropriate. Usually a 580 note indicates the relationship.

Indicator 1

Note controller

Values

- 0=Display note
- 1=Do not display note

Indicator 2

Display constant controller

Values

- #=Related item
- 8=No display constant generated

For the subfields see the [780 subfields](#).

[Intro](#) | [Resources](#) |

MARC Fields

[008](#) (Fixed Fields) | [022 041 042](#) (Numeric/Code Fields) | [100 110 111](#)(Main Entry Fields) | [130 240](#) (Uniform Title Fields) | [210 222 245 246 247](#) (Title Fields) | [250](#) (Edition Statement) | [260 300 310 321 362](#) (Descriptive Fields) | [440 490](#)(Series Fields) | [5xx \(General Comments\)](#) | [5xx's \(Major\)](#) | [5xx's \(Additional\)](#) | (Note Fields) | [6xx](#) (Subject Fields) | [700-711](#) (Name Added Entries) | [730-740](#) (Title Added Entries) | [76x-78x](#) (Linking Fields) | [8xx](#) (Series Added Entry and Holding Fields) | [84x-87x](#) (Holdings Fields) | [856](#) (Electronic Access) | [9xx](#) (Local Fields) |

8xx

Series added entries

Entries for series when the traced form differs from that on the piece. Usually paired with a 490. The 830 is the most common series added entry tag used with serials. For 800, 810, 811 see [Marc 21 Format for Bibliographic Data](#) or other [MARC documentation](#).

CONSER Standard Record

See [440](#) and [490](#) for CONSER Standard Record information.

Note: new MARBI standards may affect the relationships between 4xx and 8xx entries.

830

Series Added Entry - Uniform Title

Note: use of this field may be changing with new MARBI standards.

The most common subfields are shown below. For more see [Marc 21 Format for Bibliographic Data](#) or other [MARC documentation](#).

Indicator 1

Undefined

Values are blank

Indicator 2

Non-filing characters

Number of character positions that represent articles (the, die, la) and should be ignored during indexing.

Values

- 0=No nonfiling characters
- 1-9=Numbers of nonfiling characters present

Subfield a

Uniform title

- \$a Bulletin (Society of ...)

Subfield n

Number of part/section of work

Usually a subseries, which goes with the part in subfield p.

- \$n Part B

Subfield p

Name of part/section of work

- \$p Cities

Subfield v

Volume number/sequential designation

- \$v v.2
-

84x-87x

Holdings Data Embedded in Bibliographic Records

Holdings data, which is recorded in the bibliographic record. Not all systems use this.

For additional MFHD documentation see: [Marc 21 Format for Holdings Data](#) and [NASIGuide: Serial Holdings.](#)

856

Electronic Location and Access

Used to access electronic information. Basic subfields are listed below. See [Marc 21 Format for Bibliographic Data](#) or other [MARC documentation](#) for greater detail.

CONSER Standard Record

CONSER Standard Records contain generally-accessible links. Local or password protected links are not recorded in national level records.

Indicator 1

Access Method

Values

- #=No information provided
- 0=E-mail
- 1=FTP
- 2=Remote login (Telnet)
- 3=Dial up
- 4=HTTP (Hypertext Transfer Protocol)
- 7=Method specified in \$2

Indicator 2

Relationship

Values

- #=No information provided
- 0=Resource
- 1=Version of resource
- 2=Related resource
- 8=No display constant generated

Subfield u

Uniform Resource Locator

- \$u <http://netlibrary.com>

Subfield y

Link text

- \$y Click here to access via UM

Subfield z

Public note

- \$z An electronic book accessible via the World Wide Web

Subfield x

Non-public note

Note that does not display in the OPAC

- \$x Access is currently free through subscription to print
-

9xx

Locally defined fields

Fields used for local information. Check with your systems vendors to make sure they are not defined by them.

[Intro](#) | [Resources](#) |

MARC Fields

[008](#) (Fixed Fields) | [022](#) [041](#) [042](#) (Numeric/Code Fields) | [100](#) [110](#) [111](#) (Main Entry Fields) | [130](#) [240](#) (Uniform Title Fields) | [210](#) [222](#) [245](#) [246](#) [247](#) (Title Fields) | [250](#) (Edition Statement) | [260](#) [300](#) [310](#) [321](#) [362](#) (Descriptive Fields) | [440](#) [490](#) (Series Fields) | [5xx](#) ([General Comments](#)) | [5xx's \(Major\)](#) | [5xx's \(Additional\)](#) | (Note Fields) | [6xx](#) (Subject Fields) | [700-711](#) (Name Added Entries) | [730-740](#) (Title Added Entries) | [76x-78x](#) (Linking Fields) | [8xx](#) (Series Added Entry and Holding Fields) | [84x-87x](#) (Holdings Fields) | [856](#) (Electronic Access) | [9xx](#) (Local Fields) |

RESOURCES

- [Anglo-American Cataloguing Rules](#). 2nd ed. Chicago: American Library Association, 2002. (Updating looseleaf.) Also available online from Cataloger's Desktop: <http://www.loc.gov/cds/desktop/>
Accessed: December,31 2007.
- Archives of AUTOCAT. <http://listserv.syr.edu/archives/autocat.html>
Accessed: December,31 2007.
- [Bibliographic Formats and Standards](#). 3rd. Dublin, Ohio: OCLC, 2007. <http://www.oclc.org/bibformats/en/>
Accessed: December,31 2007.
- Campbell, Cameron J. [Basic Serials Cataloging Workshop: Trainee Manual](#). Washington, D.C.: CONSER, Library of Congress, 2005.
- [CONSER Cataloging Manual](#) Washington, D.C.: Cataloging Distribution Service, Library of Congress, 2002. (Updating looseleaf.) Also available online from Cataloger's Desktop: <http://www.loc.gov/cds/desktop/>
Accessed: December,31 2007.
- [CONSER Editing Guide](#) Washington, D.C.: Cataloging Distribution Service, Library of Congress, 1994. (Updating looseleaf.) Also available online from Cataloger's Desktop: <http://www.loc.gov/cds/desktop/>
Accessed: December,31 2007.

- CONSER Standard Record Documentation. CONSER, Library of Congress, 2007.
<http://www.loc.gov/catdir/cpsd/conserdoc.pdf>
Accessed: December,31 2007.
- CONSER Standard Record: Cheat Sheet for Catalogers. CONSER, Library of Congress, 2007.
<http://www.loc.gov/acq/conser/pdf/CheatSheetforCSR.pdf>
Accessed: December,31 2007.
- CONSER Standard Record for Serials. SCCTP Presentation, 2007.
<http://www.loc.gov/acq/conser/CONSERStandardRecord.ppt>
Accessed: January 2, 2008.
- CONSER website. <http://www.loc.gov/acq/conser/>
Accessed: December,31 2007.
- Fritz, Deborah A. Cataloging with AACR2& MARC21 for Books, Electronic Resources, Sound Recordings, Videorecordings and Serials. 2nd ed. Chicago: American Library Association, 2004. (Updating Looseleaf).
- Geer, Beverley Caraway Beatrice L., and Nancy G. Thomas. Notes for serials cataloging. 2nd ed. Englewood, Colo.: Libraries Unlimited, 1998.
- Hawkins, Les and Jean Hiron. Transforming AACR2: Using the revised rules in Chapters 9 and 12. NASIG Presentation, 2002. <http://www.loc.gov/acq/conser/aacr2002/A2slides.html>
Accessed: December,31 2007.
- ISSN home page. <http://www.issn.org/>
Accessed: September 19, 2008.
- US ISSN Center Home Page. <http://www.loc.gov/issn/>
Accessed: September 19, 2008.
- Library of Congress Rule Interpretations. Washington, D.C.: Cataloging Distribution Service, Library of Congress, 1989. (Updating looseleaf.) Also available online from Cataloger's Desktop:
<http://www.loc.gov/cds/desktop/>
Accessed: December,31 2007.
- Marc 21 Format for Bibliographic Data. Washington, D.C.: Cataloging Distribution Service, Library of

Congress. <http://www.loc.gov/marc/bibliographic/> Both versions of MARC 21 (concise and full) are available.
Accessed: July, 9 2008.

- Marc 21 Format for Holdings Data. Washington, D.C.: Cataloging Distribution Service, Library of Congress. <http://www.loc.gov/marc/holdings/echdhome.html> Both versions of MARC 21 (concise and full) are available.
Accessed: July 9, 2008.
- Marc Code List for Languages. Washington, D.C.: Cataloging Distribution Service, Library of Congress, 2007. <http://www.loc.gov/marc/languages/>
Accessed: December,31 2007.
- MARC Code Lists for Relators, Sources, Description Conventions: Other Sources. Washington, D.C.: Cataloging Distribution Service, Library of Congress, 2007. <http://www.loc.gov/marc/relators/relaothr.html>
Accessed: December,31 2007.
- Rosenberg, Frieda. NASIGuide: Serial Holdings. NASIG. http://www.nasig.org/publications_serials holdings.cfm
Accessed: August 23, 2008.
- Serials Cataloging Cooperative Training Program website. <http://www.loc.gov/acq/conser/scctp/home.html>
Accessed: December,31 2007.
- Archive of SERIALST. <http://list.uvm.edu/archives/serialst.html>
Accessed: December,31 2007.
- Shadle, Steve and Les Hawkins. Electronic Serials Cataloging Workshop: Trainee Manual. Washington, D.C.: CONSER, Library of Congress, 2002.
- Subject Cataloging Manual: Subject Headings. 5th ed. Washington, D.C.: Cataloging Distribution Service, Library of Congress, 1996. (Updating looseleaf.) Also available online from Cataloger's Desktop: <http://www.loc.gov/cds/desktop/>
Accessed: December,31 2007.
- Training Tools: Serials Cataloging. Cataloging Distribution Service, Library of Congress <http://www.loc.gov/cds/training.html#ser>
Accessed: December,31 2007.
- *Use of Fixed Fields 006/007/008 and Leader Codes in CONSER Records*. CONSER website, 2006. <http://www.loc.gov/acq/conser/ffuse.html>
Accessed: December,31 2007.

END

© Elizabeth McDonald, Beverly Geckle. This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. To view a copy of this license, visit <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.